

checkCIF/PLATON report

You have not supplied any structure factors. As a result the full set of tests cannot be run.

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: lhclilec-361

Bond precision: C-C = 0.0061 A Wavelength=0.71073

Cell: a=7.1573(4) b=16.6893(11) c=24.1380(15)
 alpha=90 beta=90 gamma=90

Temperature: 130 K

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	2883.3(3)	2883.3(3)
Space group	P 21 21 21	P 21 21 21
Hall group	P 2ac 2ab	P 2ac 2ab
Moiety formula	C28 H32 Cl2 Cu2 N2 O6	?
Sum formula	C28 H32 Cl2 Cu2 N2 O6	C28 H32 Cl2 Cu2 N2 O6
Mr	690.56	690.53
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.591	1.591
Z	4	4
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	1.705	1.705
F000	1416.0	1416.0
F000'	1420.21	
h, k, lmax	9, 23, 33	9, 21, 33
Nref	8074 [4544]	6166
Tmin, Tmax	0.743, 0.829	0.701, 0.830
Tmin'	0.375	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.701 Tmax=0.830
AbsCorr = ANALYTICAL

Data completeness= 1.36/0.76 Theta(max)= 29.573

R(reflections)= 0.0349(5394)

wR2(reflections)=
0.0817(6166)

S = 1.041

Npar= 367

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

 Alert level C

PLAT048_ALERT_1_C	MoietyFormula Not Given (or Incomplete)	Please Check
PLAT220_ALERT_2_C	NonSolvent Resd 1 C Ueq(max)/Ueq(min) Range	4.4 Ratio
PLAT222_ALERT_3_C	NonSolvent Resd 1 H Uiso(max)/Uiso(min) Range	5.5 Ratio
PLAT242_ALERT_2_C	Low 'MainMol' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of	C7 Check
PLAT341_ALERT_3_C	Low Bond Precision on C-C Bonds	0.00608 Ang.

 Alert level G

PLAT004_ALERT_5_G	Polymeric Structure Found with Maximum Dimension	1 Info
PLAT005_ALERT_5_G	No Embedded Refinement Details Found in the CIF	Please Do !
PLAT432_ALERT_2_G	Short Inter X...Y Contact C13 ..C15 .	3.19 Ang.
	1-x,-1/2+y,3/2-z =	4_646 Check
PLAT883_ALERT_1_G	No Info/Value for _atom_sites_solution_primary .	Please Do !
PLAT951_ALERT_5_G	Calculated (ThMax) and CIF-Reported Kmax Differ	2 Units

- 0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
- 0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
- 5 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
- 5 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

- 2 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
 - 3 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
 - 2 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
 - 0 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
 - 3 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check
-

checkCIF publication errors

 Alert level A

PUBL012_ALERT_1_A _publ_section_abstract is missing.
Abstract of paper in English.

- 1 **ALERT level A** = Data missing that is essential or data in wrong format
 - 0 **ALERT level G** = General alerts. Data that may be required is missing
-

Publication of your CIF

You should attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the nature of your study may justify the reported deviations from journal submission requirements and the more serious of these should be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. *checkCIF* was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

If level A alerts remain, which you believe to be justified deviations, and you intend to submit this CIF for publication in a journal, you should additionally insert an explanation in your CIF using the Validation Reply Form (VRF) below. This will allow your explanation to be considered as part of the review process.

Validation response form

Please find below a validation response form (VRF) that can be filled in and pasted into your CIF.

```
# start Validation Reply Form
_vrf_PUBL012_GLOBAL
;
PROBLEM: _publ_section_abstract is missing.
RESPONSE: ...
;
# end Validation Reply Form
```

If you wish to submit your CIF for publication in Acta Crystallographica Section C or E, you should upload your CIF via the web. If you wish to submit your CIF for publication in IUCrData you should upload your CIF via the web. If your CIF is to form part of a submission to another IUCr journal, you will be asked, either during electronic submission or by the Co-editor handling your paper, to upload your CIF via our web site.

PLATON version of 28/11/2022; check.def file version of 09/08/2022

